

KWVB

oligotrophic

mesotrophic 1

mesotrophic 2

eutrophic 1

eutrophic 2

polytrophic 1

polytrophic 2

hypertrophic

Satellite-derived trophic index to support management of small and medium-sized lakes

A result of the EU Horizon Project

EGU 2025

Many lakes in Brandenburg to manage

- The trophic state and its trend is an important information for lake management
- Data available for 294 lakes in Brandenburg (large lakes)
- Temporal resolution: Every 3 years

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- Is there a trend of the trophic state?
- What about all the other small and medium sized lakes?

Trophic index in Brandenburg

Water Samples

What

Phosphorus
Visibility depth
Chlorophyll a

When

At least 4 measurements
during April and October
better: 1 per Month

Trophic index in Brandenburg

**Water
Samples**

Some
deterministic
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**Trophic
index**

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TI = 0.5

Low Nutrients
Low visibility depths
Low Chl
→ Low primary
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High Nutrients
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Trophic index in Brandenburg

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Trophic index

Classification

Trophic class

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Trophic index in Brandenburg

Sentinel-2 satellite data and products

- Sentinel-2 is a mission of the ESA Copernicus Earth Observation programme
- Measures the reflectance of specific wavelengths (bands)
- **Temporal resolution:** one measurement every 5 days
- **Spatial resolution:** 10 – 60 m (depends on band)

Ultra blue	Visible light			Visible and near infrared				Shortwave infrared			
B1	B2	B3	B4	B5	B6	B7	B8	B9	B10	B11	B12

True Color

False Color

NDVI

Can we use sentinel-2 data to

- estimate the trophic status?
- identify trends?

Approach according to trophic index calculation

1. Manual selection of one pixel per lake
2. Pixel quality control: >80% of non-cloudy pixels identified as Water by Scene Classification Band (SCL)
3. High quality pixel: Remove all pixels which are not identified as water (clouds, shadows, etc. ...)
4. Calculation of the index per image (point of time), average per month, average per season

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Measurements
at one point

Temporal
aggregation

Normalized Difference Trophic Index (NDTrI)

Low trophic state

High trophic state

Water (203 images)

Normalized Difference Trophic Index (NDTrI)

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Water (426 images)

Water (110 images)

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$$NDTrI = \frac{(B5 - B2)}{(B5 + B2)}$$

Low trophic state:

$$B2 > B5 \rightarrow NDTrI < 0$$

High trophic state:

$$B5 > B2 \rightarrow NDTrI > 0$$

Correlation between NDTrI and trophic index

Correlation between NDTrI and trophic index

Year	Pearson correlation
2022	0.9
2021	0.83
2020	0.92
2019	0.9
2018	0.85

→ Strong correlation for each year

→ NDTrI can be used to estimate trophic state of a lake

NDTrl results 1: NDTrl status and trend

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NDTrI results 1: NDTrI status and trend

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Trophic variations between years:

- Lake-specific variations (catchment characteristic, lake morphology,)
- Systematic variations on a regional level (Weather)
- Systematic variations of methodology (Weather, sensors and algorithms)

Robust **Status** by moving average over 3 years

Trend analysis by removing systematic variations

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Robust **Status** by moving average over 3 years

Trend analysis by removing systematic variations

Over 6 years

Over 3 years

NDTrI results 2: Ranking status and trend

- Create 10 classes from NDTrI of equal range
- Classification of lakes into classes
- Relative comparison of trophic status
- Systematic variations are automatically removed

Linowsee (80001581187839)	5	3	3	4	3	3
Hölzerner See (800015828291)	6	5	5	4	4	6
Wendsee (800015874999)	6	5	5	5	5	6
Oberer Beetzsee (80001585639)	10	9	10	10	10	9
Großer Peetzigsee (80002696281791)	2	2	2	2	3	2
Witzker See (800015878959)	9	6	6	7	8	6
Üdersee (8000169626345)	2	3	2	2	2	1
Großer Lychensee (800015812799)	4	4	5	4	4	5
Röblinsee (800015811779)	6	4	4	4	4	5
Fahrlander See (8000158519249)	8	9	8	8	8	8
Großer Wentowsee (8000158152799)	10	10	9	9	10	9
Rosinsee (8000169626843291)	5	3	3	4	4	2
Liebenberger See (8000158278479)	7	7	8	6	5	7
Großer Prebelowsee (80001588129)	6	6	7	6	7	7
Flakensee (800015827891)	4	3	4	3	3	3
Großer Stechlinsee (800015815219)	1	1	1	1	1	1
	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023

Relevant long-term trend examples

Petznicksee

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Petznicksee
(800015814479)

Katerbower See

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Katerbower See
(800015886211)

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NDTrI conclusions

- Very high correlation between NDTrI and trophic index for 294 lakes in Brandenburg
- High temporal resolution of trophic state information (yearly), enables the
 - I. identifaction of trends
 - II. assessment of measures
- Results are available quickly (each year in November)
- Further lakes (within one region) can easily be integrated in the assessment
- Lakes can be assessed retroactively (data available from 2018)
- A jupyter notebook to process and download the data from the openEO platform will be available on: <https://github.com/AD4GD>

Future work

Up to now, the evaluation has been based on single pixels

For large lakes, the spatial distribution is to be included in future

→ More robust results

→ Identification of spatial variations

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For large lakes, the spatial distribution is to be included in future

- More robust results
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Thank you for your attention!

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